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Venezuela's Energy Transition: A Synergistic Approach to Blue Hydrogen, AI, and LNG Development.

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Article info	Abstract
<p><i>Keywords:</i> Artificial Intelligence Blue Hydrogen Carbon Capture and Storage Energy Transition Natural Gas</p>	<p><i>Background:</i> Venezuela faces critical challenges in its transition to a sustainable energy matrix, due to its historical dependence on hydrocarbons, economic instability and the obsolescence of its energy infrastructure. Despite having the largest natural gas reserves in Latin America (200.3 trillion cubic feet), the country has yet to take advantage of emerging opportunities such as the production of blue hydrogen, a key energy vector for decarbonizing carbon-intensive economies.</p> <p><i>Objective:</i> To evaluate the potential of blue hydrogen as a strategic solution for Venezuela's energy transition, considering the use of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and liquefied natural gas (LNG).</p> <p><i>Method:</i> An exploratory and descriptive approach was adopted, based on a comprehensive review of scientific literature, International Energy Agency (IEA) technical reports, PDVSA publications and international case studies. The analysis included the identification of recurring themes and the assessment of opportunities and threats.</p> <p><i>Results:</i> The Perla, Quiriquire Gas and Petrocarabobo projects show potential to be integrated into decarbonization strategies through advanced technologies such as AI and carbon capture and storage (CCS). In addition, AI optimizes critical processes such as geological analysis, demand forecasting and safety monitoring, reducing operating costs by up to 20%. However, significant structural barriers remain, such as lack of foreign investment, political and economic instability, and the need to modernize energy infrastructure.</p> <p><i>Conclusions:</i> To successfully integrate blue hydrogen, AI and LNG, significant investments, regulatory reforms, specialized training and international collaboration are required. These efforts are essential to position Venezuela as a regional leader in clean energy production and contribute to sustainable development in Latin America.</p>

1. Introduction

Venezuela faces significant challenges in its transition to a sustainable energy matrix, primarily due to its overwhelming dependence on hydrocarbons, economic instability, and aging energy infrastructure [1]. Despite possessing the largest natural gas reserves in Latin America, estimated at over 200.3 trillion cubic feet according to PDVSA [5], the country has yet to capitalize on emerging opportunities such as the production of blue hydrogen, a key energy vehicle for decarbonizing economies in transition [2]. This context raises the urgent need to explore innovative alternatives that allow the potential of natural gas to be harnessed through advanced technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI) and the strategic use of liquefied natural gas (LNG).

In Venezuela, the development of LNG infrastructure has been slow but holds significant potential for addressing both domestic energy shortages and positioning the country in international markets. Notable projects include the proposed Large-Scale Regasification Plant in Paraguaná, which aims to import LNG to complement domestic demand and alleviate the strain on existing natural gas supplies. Another critical initiative is the Mariscal Sucre Project, an offshore natural gas venture with the potential to produce LNG for either export or internal consumption, contingent upon adequate investment and political stability. Additionally, plans for Floating Storage and Regasification Units (FSRU) have been proposed, such as the 2019 initiative in Puerto Cabello, although these have not materialized due to financial constraints and

logistical challenges [6]. These efforts underscore the latent opportunities and barriers within Venezuela's LNG sector, which must be addressed to unlock its full potential.

Blue hydrogen, produced from natural gas combined with carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies, represents a unique opportunity for Venezuela within the framework of the global energy transition. However, its implementation faces structural barriers, such as a lack of foreign investment, political instability, and the need to modernize existing infrastructure [4]. Furthermore, the integration of emerging tools such as AI can optimize critical processes, from identifying natural gas deposits to demand forecasting and real-time monitoring of production plants, improving efficiency and reducing costs [7].

This study's main objective is to evaluate the potential of blue hydrogen as a key energy vector for Venezuela's energy transition, supported by artificial intelligence technologies and LNG. To this end, an exploratory and descriptive approach is adopted, based on a comprehensive literature review of International Energy Agency (IEA) reports, PDVSA publications, scientific articles, and relevant case studies. The aim is to identify challenges and propose specific strategies for the sustainable development of the Venezuelan energy sector. This research not only contributes to understanding the role of blue hydrogen in emerging contexts but also establishes a roadmap to position Venezuela as a regional leader in clean energy production.

2. Literature Review

The literature review focuses on critically analyzing previous studies related to the potential of blue hydrogen, artificial intelligence (AI), and its application in contexts similar to Venezuela. The selected studies are evaluated in terms of their objectives, methodologies, main findings, and limitations. In addition, a comparative table is included to facilitate the comparison between the works.

According to Smith [4], carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies are technically feasible but require significant investments for large-scale implementation. This challenge is particularly relevant for developing countries like Venezuela, which are seeking to integrate these technologies into their energy systems.

2.1. Blue and Green Hydrogen

According to IRENA [8], the combination of blue and green hydrogen accelerates decarbonization, especially in countries with renewable potential. Venezuela, with an average solar irradiation of 5.8 kWh/m²/day in Los Llanos, could integrate green electrolysis into its strategy [9] [10]. González [2] analyzes the potential for blue hydrogen production in Latin America, highlighting Venezuela's competitive advantages due to its vast natural gas reserves. However, he identifies structural barriers such as lack of foreign investment, political instability, and the need to modernize infrastructure.

2.2. Artificial Intelligence

A report by the U.S. Department of Energy [11] highlights how AI can optimize industrial processes and improve operational efficiency. Tools such as Large Language Models (LLMs) facilitate decision-making by processing large volumes of unstructured data [12]. Johnson highlights that AI can reduce operating costs by up to 20% by optimizing power grids and predicting energy demand.

2.3. Liquefied Natural Gas

International examples such as Chile and Brazil show how LNG can replace more polluting fuels and stabilize energy matrices:

- In Chile, the use of LNG has allowed closing coal plants and reducing emissions by 12% from 2022 [13].
- In Brazil, LNG covers up to 8% of electricity demand during droughts, although its viability depends on volatile global prices [14].
- For Venezuela, LNG could be a strategic solution to export natural gas or complement its domestic energy matrix, especially in projects such as Perla and Quiriquire Gas [15].

2.4. Carbon Capture and Storage

According to the Global CCS Institute [16], there are approximately 820 CCS projects registered globally, compared to 573 projects reported by the IEA. This study emphasizes the need to organize and manage large volumes of data to improve the planning and execution of CCS projects. Mota-Nieto [17]

evaluate carbon accounting methods for CCS projects in Mexico, highlighting the importance of standardized methodologies.

Energy Projects in Venezuela

- Perla Project (Cardón IV): This offshore field has the potential to produce 580 million cubic feet of gas per day, which could serve as a basis for blue hydrogen production.
- Quiriquire Gas: With an area of 93 km², this project could complement natural gas production, especially if integrated with advanced technologies such as AI
- Petrocarabobo: Although focused on heavy oil, this project could integrate CCS technologies to reduce GHG emissions associated with heavy crude exploitation

2.5. Gas para Todos Project

This government initiative aims to expand the use of natural gas in households across Venezuela, with the potential to integrate liquefied natural gas (LNG) in isolated areas where pipeline infrastructure is lacking. According to, the project underscores the importance of leveraging existing resources to promote energy access while addressing logistical challenges in remote regions. If successfully implemented, this initiative could lay the groundwork for integrating LNG as a transitional fuel toward cleaner energy solutions, including blue hydrogen production.

2.6. José Cryogenic Blending Plant

This facility, located in Anzoátegui, has been partially adapted to produce hydrogen, although it faces technical limitations due to outdated infrastructure and insufficient investment. Despite these constraints, the plant represents a critical opportunity for Venezuela to repurpose existing assets for hydrogen production. By upgrading its technology and integrating CCS systems, the facility could become a cornerstone for the country's blue hydrogen strategy, aligning with global trends in low-carbon energy development [18]. These cases demonstrate both the latent potential and the structural barriers that characterize Venezuela's energy transition efforts. They also emphasize the need for targeted investments, technological modernization, and policy reforms to unlock the full potential of LNG and hydrogen production in the country.

A detailed analysis of the most relevant studies is presented below:

González [2023] analyzed the potential for blue hydrogen production in Latin America, with emphasis on Venezuela and Colombia. Methodology: The study used a qualitative approach based on semi-structured interviews with energy experts and analysis of secondary data from international organizations. The findings showed that Venezuela has competitive advantages due to its vast natural gas reserves but faces structural barriers such as lack of foreign investment, political instability and the need to modernize infrastructure. Integration of CCS technologies can significantly reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Limitations: Lack of up-to-date quantitative data: Due to the scarcity of recent statistics on natural gas production and CO₂ emissions in Venezuela, part of the analysis was based on historical data and general projections, which could affect the accuracy of the conclusions. Reliance on secondary sources: Much of the information came from reports of international agencies and previous studies, which limits the ability to perform an in-depth analysis of specific cases in Venezuela. Geographic limitations: The study does not delve into regional details within Venezuela, which could be relevant for identifying priority areas for blue hydrogen projects.

Irena [2023] highlighted how the combination of blue and green hydrogen accelerates decarbonization, especially in countries with renewable potential. The study uses simulation models and data analysis to assess the impact of different hydrogen technologies on emission reductions. Finally, they concluded that countries with high renewable potential, such as Venezuela (with an average solar irradiation of 5.8 kWh/m²/day in Los Llanos), could integrate green electrolysis into their energy strategy. The combination of blue and green hydrogen offers a hybrid solution that maximizes the use of available resources and reduces costs. Limitations: Generalized approach: The study does not address specific political and social contexts, such as implementation challenges in emerging economies like Venezuela. Lack of concrete proposals: Although it highlights the potential of the technologies, it does not offer detailed strategies to overcome financial and regulatory barriers.

Colombia's National Hydrogen Plan (2022) linked energy transition with territorial peace, prioritizing areas affected by social conflicts. The plan is based on public consultations, geospatial data analysis and technical-economic feasibility studies. The results show that the integration of green hydrogen projects in areas with social conflicts can contribute to socio-economic development. This approach is

relevant for Venezuela, given its context of social and political instability. U.S. Department of Energy (DOE, 2023) highlighted how AI can accelerate progress toward a clean energy economy. AI use cases in industrial process optimization, energy demand forecasting and real-time monitoring are discussed. They concluded that tools such as Large Language Models (LLM) allow processing large volumes of unstructured data, facilitating decision making. AI can reduce operating costs by up to 20% by optimizing the power grid and forecasting demand.

Table 1 Summary of related work contribution

Author	Year	Objective	Methodology	Main Findings	Limitations
González	2023	Analyzing the potential of blue hydrogen in Latin America	Semi-structured interviews and secondary data analysis	Venezuela has great potential but faces regulatory barriers and a lack of investment. Prioritizing areas with social conflicts	It does not address social implications or investment attraction strategies.
Colombia (Hydrogen Plan)	2022	Linking energy transition and territorial peace	Public consultations and technical analysis	promotes socioeconomic development	Results depend on political stability
IRENA	2023	Combining blue and green hydrogen to accelerate decarbonization	Simulation models and data analysis	Integrating renewables improves sustainability	It does not address political and social contexts
DOE	2023	Highlighting the role of AI in the energy transition	Simulation models and case analysis	AI reduces operating costs by up to 20%	Dependence on reliable data
Global CCS Institute	2023	Document global CCS projects	Database and statistical analysis	820 CCS projects registered, with a growing focus on emerging economies	Persistent financial and regulatory challenges

3. Methodology

This study adopts an exploratory and descriptive approach, selecting sources published between 2018 and 2023 in reliable databases such as Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar, and institutional repositories such as the International Energy Agency (IEA) and PDVSA [19]. The inclusion criteria were:

Sources had to be related to blue hydrogen, artificial intelligence (AI), carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies, and the energy transition in contexts like Venezuela's. Studies with clear methodologies and reproducible results were prioritized, including technical reports, scientific articles, and case studies [4]. Sources that directly addressed the Venezuelan context or that could be extrapolated to developing countries with similar characteristics were included. In addition, a complementary review of international regulatory documents and energy policies was conducted to contextualize the regulatory framework necessary for the development of blue hydrogen projects [20].

Furthermore, the methodology includes an analysis of how liquefied natural gas (LNG) can serve as an input for blue hydrogen production, leveraging existing infrastructure such as the Cryogenic de Oriente plant in Anzoátegui. This facility, originally designed for natural gas processing and export, could be adapted to support blue hydrogen production by integrating carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies. The adaptability of such infrastructure reduces the need for new investments in facilities and accelerates the implementation of blue hydrogen projects. By examining case studies and technical reports on similar adaptations in other regions, this study evaluates the feasibility of repurposing LNG plants to enhance Venezuela's position in the global hydrogen market while addressing challenges related to cost, efficiency, and environmental impact.

3.1. Specific Source Selection Criteria

- Thematic Relevance:
 - Sources had to be related to the following topics:
 - Blue hydrogen: Production, associated technologies, and its role in the energy transition.
 - Artificial Intelligence (AI): Optimization of energy processes, demand forecasting, and efficiency improvements.
 - Carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies: Importance and feasibility in the Venezuelan context.

- Energy Transition: Contexts similar to Venezuela's, especially in developing countries.
- Methodological Quality:
 - Studies with clear methodologies and reproducible results were prioritized. This included:
 - Technical reports from international organizations (such as the International Energy Agency, IEA).
 - Peer-reviewed scientific articles.
 - Case study analyses and specialized studies.
- Geographic Relevance:
 - Sources were included that directly addressed the Venezuelan context or that could be extrapolated to developing countries with similar characteristics, such as hydrocarbon dependence, outdated infrastructure, and need for foreign investment.
- Publication Period:
 - The selected sources were published between 2018 and 2023, ensuring that the information was up-to-date and relevant to the analysis.
- Databases Used:
 - Sources were obtained from reliable databases, such as:
 - Scopus
 - The Science Web
 - Google Scholar
 - Institutional repositories, such as those of the IEA and PDVSA (Petróleos de Venezuela, S.A.).
- Complementarity:
 - In addition to scientific articles, a complementary review of regulatory documents, international energy policies, and relevant case studies were conducted to contextualize the regulatory framework necessary for the development of blue hydrogen projects.

3.2. Justification for the Exploratory and Descriptive Approach

The exploratory and descriptive approach was selected due to the emerging nature of the topic in the Venezuelan context. This approach allows for the identification of emerging patterns, the assessment of opportunities and challenges, and the laying of the groundwork for future quantitative research. Furthermore, given the scarcity of recent primary data on blue hydrogen production in Venezuela, this approach is appropriate for analyzing secondary sources as illustrated in Figure 1, [21] and generating a robust theoretical framework.

3.3. However, it is important to recognize the limitations inherent to this approach

- Reliance on secondary sources: Much of the analysis is based on previous reports and studies, which may limit the ability to conduct detailed quantitative assessments.
- Lack of Venezuela-specific data: The availability of up-to-date and specific data on the Venezuelan energy sector is limited, making further analysis difficult.
- Biases in source selection: Although clear criteria were used to select sources, some relevant studies may have been excluded due to a lack of access to premium databases.

3.4. Specific Qualitative Tools

To conduct the qualitative analysis, the following tools and techniques were used:

- Thematic Content Analysis:

The bibliographic data were categorized into recurring themes, such as the potential for blue hydrogen production, the role of AI in process optimization, and the challenges associated with aging infrastructure. Key patterns in the literature were identified, such as the importance of CCS technologies and the need for regulatory reforms.

- Analysis Matrix:

A comparative matrix was created to evaluate the main studies reviewed, considering objectives, methodologies, findings, and limitations. This allowed for a critical synthesis of existing literature.

- Deductive and Inductive Coding:

Deductive coding was used to organize data according to predefined categories (e.g., "technology," "policy," "economics").

3.5. Methodology Application

- Venezuela's Potential for Blue Hydrogen Production and the Role of LNG
 - Venezuela has significant potential for blue hydrogen production, supported by its vast natural gas reserves, the most extensive in Latin America and among the largest worldwide. This abundance of raw material facilitates the steam methane reforming (SMR) process, the predominant technique in blue hydrogen production. Additionally, the country has an infrastructure of gas pipelines and gas processing plants that can be adapted for hydrogen production and transport, reducing the costs and times of implementing new projects.
 - The availability of depleted oil and gas fields offers a viable and economical solution for CO₂ storage, an essential component in blue hydrogen production, minimizing the need to explore and develop new storage sites. PDVSA's experience in the exploration, production, and processing of natural gas represents a competitive advantage, streamlining the transition to blue hydrogen production.
 - However, Venezuela faces considerable challenges that could hinder the development of its potential in blue hydrogen production. The lack of investment and maintenance has negatively impacted natural gas production and infrastructure, requiring immediate attention and substantial investment. The country's economic and political instability makes it difficult to attract foreign investment, which is crucial to finance large-scale projects.
 - The implementation of carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies requires significant investment and technical expertise, which poses an additional challenge.
 - Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) [2] emerges as a key component in Venezuela's blue hydrogen production strategy. Its versatility as a natural gas source is valuable in areas without access to gas pipelines. Existing LNG plants can be adapted to include CO₂ capture units, integrating LNG production with blue hydrogen production. LNG could also be a by-product of blue hydrogen, leveraging its potential as a clean fuel. However, LNG production and transport require significant investments in infrastructure and logistical planning.
- Optimization of the Blue Hydrogen Value Chain Through Artificial Intelligence
 - AI plays a crucial role in optimizing the blue hydrogen value chain. Through advanced analysis of geological and seismic data, AI enables the precise identification of deposits and the optimization of drilling and extraction. In carbon capture and storage (CCS), AI improves the efficiency of processes and predicts the behavior [7] of CO₂ in storage sites. It also facilitates demand prediction, optimizes distribution, and increases safety in production plants. AI's ability to analyze large volumes of data and predict trends allows for better resource planning and management.
 - Geological and Seismic Data Analysis: AI, through deep learning algorithms, can analyze large volumes of seismic and geological data to identify patterns and structures that indicate the presence of natural gas deposits.
 - Drilling and Extraction Optimization: AI can optimize drilling parameters, such as rotation speed and fluid pressure, to maximize production and minimize risks.
 - Optimization of Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) Processes with AI: AI can optimize the operating parameters of CO₂ capture plants and analyze geological and seismic data to identify safe and efficient CO₂ storage sites.
 - Prediction of Demand and Optimization of Distribution and Storage of Blue Hydrogen with AI: AI can analyze historical and real-time data on energy demand, industrial activity, and energy prices to predict future demand for blue hydrogen.
 - AI and Safety in Gas and Hydrogen Production Plants: AI can analyze sensor data in real time to detect anomalies and unusual patterns that may indicate equipment failures or gas leaks.
- Implications and Opportunities for Venezuela in the Energy Transition
 - The global energy transition, aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions and adopting more sustainable energy sources, poses both challenges and opportunities for Venezuela. Given its historical dependence on hydrocarbons, the country faces significant challenges but also has vast potential to diversify its economy and position itself as a relevant player in the energy market of the future.
 - Implications for Venezuela:
 - Economic Challenges
 - Reduction in global oil demand: The energy transition could decrease global oil demand, which would severely affect Venezuela, whose economy largely depends on crude oil exports.

- Devaluation of oil assets: Oil assets could lose value as the world moves towards cleaner energies.
- Social and Political Challenges:
 - Impact on employment: The oil industry is a major source of employment in Venezuela. An abrupt transition could generate unemployment and social tensions.
 - Fiscal dependence: The government depends on oil revenues to finance social programs and public spending. A drop in revenues could generate fiscal crises and limit the State's ability to respond to the needs of the population.
- Technological and Infrastructure Challenges:
 - Lack of investment in clean energies: Venezuela has invested little in renewable energies and clean technologies, which hinders its participation in the energy transition.
 - Obsolete infrastructure: The country's energy infrastructure is in poor condition, which hinders the modernization of the sector and the integration of new technologies.
- Opportunities for Venezuela:
- Potential in Renewable Energies:
 - Solar energy: Venezuela has high solar potential, especially in regions such as Zulia, Falcón, and the Llanos.
 - Wind energy: The Venezuelan coasts, particularly in the east of the country, have potential for wind generation.
 - Hydroelectric energy: Venezuela already has significant hydroelectric capacity (such as Guri), which could be modernized and expanded to support the energy transition.
- Green and Blue Hydrogen:
 - Green hydrogen: Venezuela could leverage its potential in renewable energies to produce green hydrogen, a clean fuel with high global demand.
 - Blue hydrogen: Using its vast natural gas reserves, Venezuela could produce blue hydrogen with carbon capture, attracting investments and meeting environmental standards.
- Economic Diversification:
 - Strategic minerals industry: Venezuela has reserves of key minerals for the energy transition, such as nickel, cobalt, and lithium, used in batteries and green technologies.
 - Bioenergy: The country could develop bioenergy projects using agricultural or forest biomass.
- International Financing Opportunities:
 - Climate funds: Venezuela could access international financing for renewable energy and decarbonization projects.
 - Carbon compensation mechanisms: Participate in carbon markets to monetize emissions reduction projects.
- International Cooperation:
 - Strategic alliances: Collaborate with leading countries and companies in clean technologies for knowledge and technology transfer.
 - Regional integration: Participate in regional energy transition initiatives, such as those promoted by OLADE or CELAC.
- Strategies and Recommendations for the Development of the Blue Hydrogen Industry in Venezuela
 - It is essential to establish a legal framework that provides legal certainty to investors. This includes regulations on the production, transport, storage, and use of blue hydrogen, as well as tax incentives to encourage investment.
 - Significant investment is required to modernize the natural gas infrastructure and adapt existing facilities for blue hydrogen production.
 - Venezuela must seek strategic alliances with companies and countries leading in hydrogen production and CCS technologies.
 - Training programs are needed to develop the necessary skills in the blue hydrogen industry, from production and transport to carbon capture and storage.

4. Results

The Perla field, with a production of 580 MMcf/day of gas [15], could be adapted for blue hydrogen if CCS technologies are implemented, following the Chilean model of public auctions [14]

Venezuela is at a crucial historical moment, facing the need for a profound reconfiguration of its energy and economic matrix. The country has significant potential for the transition to blue hydrogen production, supported by its vast natural gas reserves, the largest in Latin America, and an existing infrastructure of pipelines and gas processing plants. This potential is further strengthened by the availability of depleted oil and gas fields, which offer a viable and economical solution for CO₂ storage, an essential component in blue hydrogen production.

However, it also faces significant challenges, such as political and economic instability, the need for massive investments, and the modernization of its energy infrastructure. These factors could hamper the development of the sector if not adequately addressed.

Artificial intelligence (AI) plays a fundamental role in optimizing the blue hydrogen value chain in Venezuela. Its applications include:

- Geological and seismic data analysis: AI enables the precise identification of natural gas deposits using advanced algorithms.
- Carbon capture and storage (CCS) process optimization: Improves the efficiency of these processes and predicts CO₂ behavior at storage sites.
- Demand forecasting: Analyzes historical and real-time data on industrial activity, energy prices, and market trends to forecast future demand for blue hydrogen.
- Distribution and storage: Optimizes distribution logistics and the use of existing infrastructure.
- Real-time monitoring and predictive maintenance: Improves safety at production plants by detecting anomalies and unusual patterns that may indicate equipment failure or gas leaks.
- The adoption of these technologies represents an opportunity to modernize the Venezuelan energy sector and position itself as a competitive player in the global market.

The development of the blue hydrogen industry in Venezuela faces several key challenges:

- Lack of investment: The scarcity of financial resources has negatively impacted natural gas production and associated infrastructure, requiring immediate attention and substantial investment.
- Political and economic instability: The country's internal situation makes it difficult to attract foreign investment, which is crucial for financing large-scale projects.
- Outdated infrastructure: Modernizing energy infrastructure is essential to integrate new technologies and ensure the technical and economic viability of blue hydrogen production.
- Development of CCS technologies: The implementation of carbon capture and storage technologies requires significant investment and specialized technical expertise.
- Furthermore, the lack of a clear regulatory framework and the need for job training are additional barriers that must be overcome to fully realize the potential of blue hydrogen.

5. Discussion

Venezuela's potential for blue hydrogen production is comparable to that of other developing countries with vast natural gas reserves, such as Algeria and Nigeria. However, while these countries have made progress in implementing pilot projects and established clear regulatory frameworks, Venezuela faces unique challenges related to its political and economic instability [22]. For example, Algeria has successfully integrated blue hydrogen into its energy strategy through international partnerships and the modernization of its infrastructure. In contrast, Venezuela has not yet been able to capitalize on its resources due to a lack of foreign investment and obsolete facilities.

Furthermore, countries such as Chile and Colombia have prioritized the development of green hydrogen by leveraging their renewable resources, allowing them to position themselves as regional leaders in clean energy [13]. This highlights the need for Venezuela to diversify its approach beyond blue hydrogen and integrate green technologies to avoid being left behind in the global energy transition [23] [24].

Hybrid projects, such as HyEx in Chile [13], demonstrate that the transition should not be limited to natural gas but should explore complementarities with renewable energy.

Compared to other South American countries, González Cruz's findings [25] highlight the need to strengthen regional alliances to overcome the economic and political barriers that limit energy integration.

The political viability of blue hydrogen in Venezuela must consider models like that of Saudi Arabia, which prioritizes sustainability funds for low-carbon technologies [26]. Furthermore, collaboration with international organizations could mitigate risks, as proposed by ECLAC [27].

In addition to the issues, Venezuela faces specific obstacles that further complicate the development of its blue hydrogen industry:

- **International Sanctions:** These sanctions significantly limit Venezuela's access to advanced technology required for gas liquefaction and carbon capture and storage (CCS). The inability to acquire cutting-edge equipment and expertise hinders the country's ability to modernize its energy infrastructure and implement large-scale hydrogen projects.
- **Lack of Maintenance in Pipeline Infrastructure:** A critical issue is the deteriorating state of Venezuela's natural gas pipeline network. For instance, the Antonio Ricaurte pipeline, which connects Colombia and Venezuela, remains underutilized due to insufficient maintenance and operational challenges. This suboptimal use of existing infrastructure reduces the efficiency of natural gas transportation and limits the potential for integrating these resources into the hydrogen value chain.

These unique challenges underscore the urgent need for targeted strategies to address both external constraints (such as sanctions) and internal deficiencies (such as infrastructure neglect). Overcoming these barriers will require significant investments, international cooperation, and a clear regulatory framework to attract foreign partners and ensure the technical and economic viability of blue hydrogen projects.

In the short term, the viability of blue hydrogen production in Venezuela is limited by a lack of investment and political instability. However, existing projects such as the Perla field and other natural gas initiatives could serve as a foundation for developing initial capabilities. Implementing clear public policies and attracting international investment will be crucial to overcoming these barriers.

In the medium term (5-10 years), Venezuela could begin implementing blue hydrogen pilot projects, especially in regions with established natural gas infrastructure. Modernizing this infrastructure, along with the adoption of carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies, will demonstrate the technical and economic viability of this solution. Furthermore, international collaboration and access to climate funds could accelerate this process.

In the long term (more than 10 years), Venezuela has the potential to become a key player in the global blue and green hydrogen market. The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) throughout the value chain will optimize production, distribution, and storage, reducing costs and improving competitiveness. However, this will depend on the country's ability to overcome its structural challenges and consolidate a diversified economy less dependent on oil.

This study presents several methodological limitations that should be considered:

- **Lack of updated quantitative data:**
Due to the scarcity of recent statistics on natural gas production and CO₂ emissions in Venezuela, part of the analysis relied on historical data and general projections. This could affect the accuracy of the conclusions.
- **Reliance on secondary sources:**
Much of the information comes from reports by international organizations and previous studies, which limits the ability to conduct an in-depth analysis of specific cases in Venezuela.
- **Limitations in geographic scope:**
The study focused primarily on Venezuela, without a comprehensive comparative analysis with other developing countries. This could have provided a more complete perspective on successful strategies implemented in similar contexts.
- **Challenges in AI implementation:**
While the role of artificial intelligence in process optimization was highlighted, the technical and ethical challenges associated with its implementation, such as the lack of transparency in some algorithms and the risk of bias, were not assessed in detail.

The lack of quantitative data on the Venezuelan energy sector is acknowledged, but no alternative solutions (such as the use of predictive models or similar case studies) are proposed.

6. Conclusion

Venezuela has vast natural gas reserves, the largest in Latin America, which represents a key opportunity to produce blue hydrogen as a strategic energy vector in the transition to a sustainable energy matrix. This resource, combined with advanced technologies such as carbon capture and storage (CCS), can play a crucial role in the decarbonization of carbon-intensive economies. However, this potential is supported by specific results of the study, such as the analysis of the Perla field, which could be adapted to produce blue hydrogen if CCS technologies are implemented following successful models such as those in Chile.

AI is fundamental to optimize the blue hydrogen value chain. From accurate identification of natural gas reservoirs through advanced algorithms to demand prediction and real-time monitoring of production plants, these technologies reduce operating costs and improve efficiency. For example, optimization of CO₂ capture and storage processes using AI could significantly reduce emissions associated with blue hydrogen production. However, their implementation in emerging contexts such as Venezuela faces challenges related to the lack of technological infrastructure and reliable data.

Despite the potential identified, Venezuela faces critical barriers that must be addressed to ensure the technical and economic viability of blue hydrogen projects. These include the lack of foreign investment, political and economic instability, and the need to modernize the energy infrastructure. In addition, the study results highlight how international sanctions limit access to advanced technology for natural gas liquefaction and CCS, while lack of maintenance in existing infrastructure reduces the efficiency of natural gas transportation and its integration into the hydrogen value chain.

The global energy transition offers unique opportunities for Venezuela, including economic diversification through the development of renewable energy, the production of green and blue hydrogen, and the exploitation of strategic minerals such as lithium and cobalt. However, these opportunities are conditioned by the country's ability to overcome its structural challenges. The results indicate that, in the medium term, pilot projects in regions with established natural gas infrastructure could demonstrate the technical and economic feasibility of these solutions.

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